

Autoencoder-Optimized Geometric Constellation Shaping for Unamplified Coherent Optical Links

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Abstract: Using end-to-end deep learning, we experimentally demonstrate the optimized design of geometric constellation shaping for coherent unamplified links. A power budget gain of more than 2 dB is demonstrated for 8-ary constellations. © 2022 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Targeting the reduction of cost and power consumption, the recent coherent short-reach 400ZR standard already accounts for optical unamplified short-reach systems [1]. However, this option severely affects the power budget, while also introducing a new challenging constraint: due to the absence of a transmitter-side optical amplifier (booster), the system becomes highly sensitive to the peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) [2, 3]. This impairment has been identified as a peak-power-constraint (PPC), typical to unamplified systems [4]. In [2], we have demonstrated that the application of digital clipping can effectively reduce the PAPR of complex QAM constellations, thereby highly improving the achievable power budget. An important question then arises: is the typical use of QAM formats the most suitable for unamplified transmission? In this regard, geometric constellation shaping (GCS) [5] may appear as a useful alternative to classical QAM formats, to make better use of the complex coordinates of the constellation points, while accounting for the limitations of unamplified systems. On the note of GCS optimization in a constrained system, few recent works have proposed the usage of *autoencoders* [6], designed for joint optimization of the transmitter and receiver through end-to-end deep learning. However, while several works can be found in the literature that resort to the usage of autoencoders for the optical fiber channel, the issue of peak-power constrained constellation optimization is yet to be addressed. In this work, we employ an *autoencoder* that optimizes signal modulation for unamplified coherent systems, and compare its performance with well-known constellations.

2. An Autoencoder-based Approach

Figure 1a shows the architecture of the autoencoder (AE). The AE is a tensorflow-based implementation, similar to the one proposed in [6], with the modified normalization layer to match the peak-power-constraint (PPC). For the optimization, we used the categorical cross-entropy as the loss function, with an Adam optimizer. The AE follows a symbol-wise implementation; hence, it has M inputs and M outputs, with M being the order of the constellation we aim at optimizing. At the transmitter-side, the AE is composed of an encoder, which is implemented by a neural network (NN), followed by a separate in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) peak normalization to impose the PPC. An additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel is added and the signal is decoded at the decoder NN. Training is done with 4×10^6 randomly generated symbols and using back-propagation to update the weights of the NNs that constitute the encoder and decoder. To ensure optimal convergence of the AE, for each studied scenario, we realize 50 independent training loops, from which we choose the constellation that achieves the minimum loss. Given the optimal constellation for each scenario, with M points, we save the in-phase and quadrature values for the constellation. This M -ary constellation (henceforth referred to as M -AE) is then fed to the optical system. The chosen constellations, for each M , are shown in Fig. 1b. Note that the constellation for 16-AE is converging towards square-QAM, as this is the format that minimizes the real-value PAPR. For the case of 8-AE, the AE converged to a well-defined square-8QAM constellation [7]. In 32-AE, the square-like manner distribution of the

Fig. 1: a) Block diagram of the autoencoder-based constellation optimization with each constellation as an inset with the corresponding real-value PAPR. b) Diagram of the experimental setup. AE: Autoencoder-optimized constellation. rect-QAM: rectangular-QAM.

Fig. 2: Experimentally-obtained attenuation curves for each constellation format and for a) $M = 8$, b) $M = 16$ and c) $M = 32$.

outer symbols allows for PAPR reduction, while the inner symbols are approaching a Gaussian geometry, taking advantage of the AWGN channel model.

3. Performance Analysis

As a first performance indicator, we identify the PAPR of each constellation in Fig. 1b. These values were collected using Monte Carlo simulations with 1000 independent realizations of different transmitted data patterns of length 2^{17} , and including a root-raised-cosine (RRC) pulse shaping function with the optimum roll-off of $\alpha = 0.4$ [3]. Note that we are measuring the real-value PAPR, as opposed to the absolute value of the complex signal. This is an important observation, as the peak launched power is ultimately determined by the PAPR of the individual I and Q components of the transmitted signal. For this reason, the 8-PSK constellation has a higher PAPR than rect-8QAM and 8-AE. With the autoencoder optimization, we reduce the PAPR by 3.1 dB when compared to 8-QAM. When we increase the constellation order, we have a lower margin for PAPR reduction and, in fact, the gain in PAPR reduces: 32-AE has a PAPR of only 0.8 dB lower than 32-QAM.

4. Experimental Validation

Figure 1b shows a diagram of the experimental setup. At the transmitter-side, the digital signal processing (DSP) block sends samples to the 120 GSa/s arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) with 8-bit resolution, which then feeds the ~ 35 GHz bandwidth dual-polarization (DP) in-phase and quadrature modulator (IQM). The DP-IQM is driven with a tunable laser source (TLS) operating at 1550 nm with 13 dBm of optical power and with 100 kHz linewidth. Another TLS with an optical power of 13 dBm is used as a local oscillator (LO) at the receiver-side. The 40 GHz bandwidth coherent receiver feeds the signal to a four-port real-time oscilloscope with 70 GHz bandwidth that digitizes the signal at 200 GSa/s. A variable optical attenuator (VOA) is used to evaluate the link power budget. The *genie-aided* DSP applies Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization, complex constant-modulus algorithm (CMA) equalization, frequency recovery followed by carrier phase estimation and a final real-value 4×4 least mean squares equalizer. The transmitted signals have a symbol rate of 60 Gbaud, to which we apply an RRC pulse shaping function with roll-off $\alpha = 0.4$, thereby minimizing the PAPR imposed by the pulse shaping function [3].

The optical back-to-back received constellations are shown in Fig. 2a. From these figures, we verify the sub-optimal use of rectangular-QAM for unamplified systems due to the decreased euclidean distance between constellation points. The experimentally-achieved attenuation curves are shown in Figures 2b and 2c. For the case of $M = 8$, we observe AE power budget gains in accordance to the PAPR decrease, roughly yielding 2 dB and 3 dB gap to the 8-PSK and 8-QAM curves, respectively. For the case of $M = 32$, 32-AE and 32-QAM achieve similar performance, outperforming rect-32-QAM, as expected, and showing a 0.6 dB gain to 32-QAM.

5. Conclusions

Employing end-to-end deep learning, in this work, we have developed and experimentally validated an autoencoder providing optimized geometric constellation shaping for unamplified coherent short-reach applications, which are governed by a peak-power constraint. We have achieved significant gains through the geometric optimization of cross-QAM. Particularly, power budget gains of 2–3 dB are experimentally demonstrated for 8-ary constellations.

This work was partially supported by FEDER, through the CENTRO 2020 programme, project ORCIP (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-022141), SOCA (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000010), LANDMARK (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-031527), and RETIOT (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-016432), and by FCT/MCTES through project FreeComm-B5G (UIDB/EEA/50008/2020) and PhD grants SFRH/BD/143498/2019 and UI/BD/151328/2021. Fernando P. Guiomar acknowledges a fellowship from “la Caixa” Foundation (ID 100010434), code LCF/BQ/PR20/11770015.

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